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The impact of term-weighting schemes and similarity measures on extractive multi-document text summarization

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Abstract

Automatic text summarization is currently a topic of great interest in many knowledge fields. Extractive multi-document text summarization methods aim to reduce the textual information from a document collection by covering the main content and reducing the redundant information. In the scientific literature, there are different approaches related to term-weighting schemes and similarity measures, which are necessary for implementing an automatic summary system. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no studies to analyze the performance of the different schemes and measures. In this paper, all possible combinations of the most common term-weighting schemes and similarity measures used in the extractive multi-document text summarization field have been implemented, compared, and analyzed. Experiments have been performed with Document Understanding Conferences (DUC) datasets, and the model performance has been assessed with eight Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation (ROUGE) metrics and the execution time. Results show that the best term-weighting scheme is the term-frequency inverse-sentence-frequency scheme, and the best similarity measure is the cosine similarity. Even more, the combination formed by both of them has obtained the best average results in 87.5% of ROUGE scores compared to the other combinations.

Keywords: Multi-document summarization, Extractive summary, Term-weighting, Similarity.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the amount of digital documents contained in the World Wide Web has grown enormously in any topic; and furthermore, the Internet users increasingly demand such information as quickly as possible. According to Fan & Bifet (2013), by means of text mining tools it is possible to extract the most important information from a document collection. Particularly, these tools should be able to automatically reduce this textual information by generating a summary (Hashimi et al., 2015), which covers the main content of the documents and avoids the redundancy of information.

Different text summarization methods have been addressed in the scientific literature. First, a summary can be query-oriented or generic. A query-oriented summary needs a query given by the user, which describes a specific information requirement (Huang et al., 2010). On the other side, a generic summary does not require any query, since its aim is to cover all the information. Text summarization methods can also be abstractive or extractive (Wan, 2008). While abstractive summaries can contain words and sentences that do not exist in the original documents, extractive summaries select complete sentences from the document collection. Another classification for text summarization methods depends on the origin of the text: single-document summaries reduce the textual information of a single document, and multi-document summaries select subsets of text from a whole document collection (Zajic et al., 2008).

The extractive generic multi-document text summarization problem can be solved by using several approaches. Over the last few years, this problem has been addressed using techniques based on complex networks or multilayer network models, as in Amancio et al. (2012) and Tohalino & Amancio (2018), respectively. In fact, graph-based techniques, such as co-occurrence networks, have also been proposed in other text mining tasks (see e.g. Akimushkin et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2018). In addition, the use of the term-based vector space model (VSM) is very common too (Salton & Buckley, 1988). In this case, the text summarization problem is based on measuring the similarity between texts, so the VSM has been used in this work to address the problem.

For the vector space model, every sentence is represented as a term vector, and a similarity measure is used for pairwise comparison between sentences.

In addition, different approaches can be used to solve this problem. On the one hand, several term-weighting schemes can be found in the literature. The term-frequency inverse-sentence-frequency scheme ($tf - isf$) is one of the most used ones (see e.g. Alguliev et al., 2011a). Other approaches as the relative-term-frequency smooth-inverse-sentence-frequency scheme ($rtf - sisf$) (Mendoza et al., 2014) and the Okapi BM25 scheme (Alguliyev et al., 2019) have also been used. On the other hand, different similarity measures can be considered. The cosine similarity is one of the most used ones in the literature (see e.g. Alguliev et al., 2011a). Other similarity measures have also been applied, such as the Jaccard similarity (Alguliev et al., 2015), the overlap similarity (Alguliev et al., 2015), and the RRN similarity (Alguliyev et al., 2019). Finally, the Normalized Google Distance (NGD) has also been used in several works (see e.g. Alguliev et al., 2012a).

In this paper, the extractive generic multi-document text summarization problem is addressed to compare the performance of the different combinations of the term-weighting schemes and similarity measures that are used in this context. After a review of the related works, the different term-weighting schemes and similarity measures used in multi-document text summarization have been described, implemented, and compared through different experiments. The experiments have been performed with Document Understanding Conferences (DUC) datasets, and have been evaluated with Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation (ROUGE) metrics. The main contributions of this paper are the following ones:

- The three different term-weighting schemes used in multi-document text summarization have been studied and analyzed.
- The five different similarity measures used in multi-document text summarization have been considered.
- An extensive comparative study has been performed among all the possible combinations of term-weighting schemes and similarity measures (a total of fifteen).
- The experiments have been evaluated with a total of eight ROUGE scores: ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-3, ROUGE-4, ROUGE-L, ROUGE-W, ROUGE-SU, and ROUGE-SU4.
- A descriptive statistical analysis has been carried out based on the quality results obtained, including the average and the Pearson's coefficient

of variation.

- The computational cost of the different term-weighting schemes and similarity measures has also been studied and compared.
- The best term-weighting schemes and similarity measures, taking into account the quality metrics (ROUGE scores) and the execution time, have been highlighted.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The state-of-the-art is presented in Section 2. Section 3 includes the formulation of the extractive multi-document text summarization problem. In Section 4, the different term-weighting schemes and similarity measures are explained. Section 5 details the datasets, the evaluation metrics, the experimental settings, and the results obtained in the experiments. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions and the future work.

2. Related work

In this section, a review of the state-of-the-art related to term-weighting schemes and similarity measures for extractive multi-document text summarization is presented.

In the first place, Table 1 reports on the related works reviewed. They are shown in chronological order. The term-weighting scheme and the similarity measure used in every work are indicated. In addition, the different ROUGE scores used in each related work are also shown.

Year	Work	Term-weighting scheme	Similarity measure	ROUGE score
2010	Aliguliyev (2010)	-	NGD	2, SU4
2011	Alguliev et al. (2011a)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	2, SU4
2011	Alguliev et al. (2011b)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2
2011	Alguliev et al. (2011c)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, SU4
2011	Alguliev et al. (2011d)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, L, SU
2012	Alguliev et al. (2012a)	$tf - isf$	NGD	1, 2, L, SU4
2012	Alguliev et al. (2012b)	$tf - isf$	NGD	-
2012	Alguliev et al. (2012c)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2
2013	Alguliev et al. (2013a)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, SU4
2013	Alguliev et al. (2013b)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, W
2013	Alguliev et al. (2013c)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, L, SU
2014	Mendoza et al. (2014)	$rtf - sisf$	Cosine	1, 2, SU4
2015	Alguliev et al. (2015)	$tf - isf$	Cosine, Jaccard, overlap	1, 2, SU4
2015	Saleh et al. (2015)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	2, L
2015	Umam et al. (2015)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, L, SU
2016	Saleh & Kadhim (2016)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	2, L
2017	Jung et al. (2017)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	-
2018	Rautray & Balabantaray (2018)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	-
2019	Alguliyev et al. (2019)	Okapi BM25	RRN	-
2019	Cho et al. (2019)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, SU4
2019	Patel et al. (2019)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2, 4, L, SU4
2020	Bidoki et al. (2020)	$tf - isf$	Cosine	1, 2

Table 1: Related works on extractive multi-document text summarization.

The most commonly used term-weighting scheme in the scientific literature is the term-frequency inverse-sentence-frequency scheme ($tf - isf$). The term frequency factor (tf) has been used in many term-weighting systems for measuring the frequency of occurrence of the terms. However, this factor cannot ensure an acceptable text retrieval performance by itself. For this reason, the inverse sentence frequency factor (isf) is necessary. It varies inversely with the number of sentences in which a term occurs. As can be seen in Table 1, $tf - isf$ scheme has been the most widely used scheme in the context of extractive multi-document text summarization.

Mendoza et al. (2014) used other kind of term-weighting scheme. Specifically, a modification of the traditional $tf - isf$ scheme, i.e., the relative-term-frequency smooth-inverse-sentence-frequency scheme ($rtf - sisf$). Both factors in this scheme have modifications, i.e., the rtf factor takes into account the number of occurrences of the most frequent term in the sentence, and the $sisf$ factor makes a correction by adding one more occurrence of the term.

Finally, Okapi BM25 represents another term-weighting scheme (Aliguliyev et al., 2019). It is one of the most widely used information retrieval

functions by search engines to assign term weights according to their relevance. Okapi BM25 was developed as a term-weighting model sensitive to the term frequency and the document length.

With respect to the similarity measures for extractive multi-document text summarization, the cosine similarity is the most widely used. It is a symmetric similarity, and it measures the resemblance between two sentences. Most of the related works have used this similarity measure, as reported in Table 1.

Alguliev et al. (2015) studied Jaccard and overlap, which represent other two similarity measures. The Jaccard similarity is based on the cosine similarity but its formulation is different, whereas the overlap similarity is an asymmetric similarity measure. Both the Jaccard and overlap similarities normalize the inner product differently from the cosine similarity.

RRN is another similarity measure (Alguliyev et al., 2019). It ensures that if there are many common terms between two sentences, they are very similar.

Finally, the NGD similarity measures the number of hits returned by the Google search engine for a given set of terms, and it was adapted to the extractive multi-document text summarization problem as a similarity measure and applied in Aliguliyev (2010), Alguliev et al. (2012a), and Alguliev et al. (2012b).

3. Problem definition

This section presents the formulation of the extractive multi-document text summarization problem. Let $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_N\}$ be a set with N documents. D can be represented as the set with all the n sentences from the documents in the collection, i.e., $D = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$, where s_i is the corresponding i -th sentence of the document collection and n is the number of sentences contained in D .

The representation of the document collection D is also based on the term-based vector space model. Now, let $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ be a set with the m different terms from the document collection, where t_k is the corresponding k -th term. Every sentence s_i is represented as a vector of weights, $s_i = (w_{i1}, w_{i2}, \dots, w_{im})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where w_{ik} is the weight of the term t_k in the sentence s_i . In the field of information systems, there are different approaches for weighting schemes. Term-weighting schemes have been widely used for extractive summarization methods. However, in other fields,

concept-weighting schemes are used, such as in information retrieval (see e.g. Boubekour & Azzoug, 2013) or in document indexing and classification (see e.g. Tahayna et al., 2010). The main difference between them is that concept-weighting schemes include semantic information based on the mapping of words in concepts or in predefined sets of compound concepts. The different existing term-weighting schemes are described later in Subsection 4.1.

Taking into account the weights w_{ik} , the main content of the document collection D can be represented as the average weights of all terms in T by means of the mean vector $O = (o_1, o_2, \dots, o_m)$. Each component of this vector is calculated as:

$$o_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n w_{ik}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (1)$$

These weights are used to calculate the similarity $sim(s_i, s_j)$, which considers the resemblance between the pair of sentences $s_i = (w_{i1}, w_{i2}, \dots, w_{im})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $s_j = (w_{j1}, w_{j2}, \dots, w_{jm})$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. The similarity measure can also be calculated by different ways, which are described in Subsection 4.2.

Once the term-weighting scheme and the similarity measure have been selected, the goal of the extractive multi-document text summarization problem is to generate a summary $S \subset D$ taking into account three aspects:

- Content coverage: the main topic of the document collection D must be covered in the summary S by including the suitable sentences.
- Redundancy reduction: similar sentences from the document collection must not be repeated in the summary S , that is, redundant sentences should be avoided in favor of more suitable ones.
- Length: the summary S must have a fixed length L with a defined tolerance.

The proposed problem implies the optimization of the content coverage and the redundancy reduction simultaneously. Because these two objectives are conflicting to each other, a multi-objective optimization approach is the best way to address this problem.

The first objective, $\Phi_{Cov}(X)$, refers to the content coverage criterion. It is expressed as the similarity between each sentence $s_i \in S$ and the set of

sentences in the document collection D , which is represented by the mean vector O . Hence, the following function should be maximized:

$$\Phi_{Cov}(X) = \sum_{i=1}^n sim(s_i, O) \cdot x_i, \quad (2)$$

where $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is a binary decision variable which considers the presence or absence ($x_i = 1$ or $x_i = 0$) of the sentence s_i in the summary S . In this way, the solution representation (the decision vector) is defined as $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$.

The second objective to optimize, $\Phi_{ReR}(X)$, concerns the redundancy reduction criterion. A second binary decision variable $y_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ is needed. It is related to the simultaneous presence ($y_{ij} = 1$ or $y_{ij} = 0$ otherwise) of the pair of sentences s_i and s_j in the summary S . Then, for each pair of sentences $s_i, s_j \in S$, the similarity should be minimized, in other words, the redundancy reduction should be maximized. The following function is formulated for that purpose, so it should be maximized:

$$\Phi_{ReR}(X) = \frac{1}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n sim(s_i, s_j) \cdot y_{ij} \right) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i}. \quad (3)$$

Finally, the multi-objective extractive multi-document text summarization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\max \Phi(X) = \{\Phi_{Cov}(X), \Phi_{ReR}(X)\}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{subject to } L - \varepsilon \leq \sum_{i=1}^n l_i \cdot x_i \leq L + \varepsilon, \quad (5)$$

being l_i the length of the sentence s_i and ε the tolerance for the summary length constraint L , which is calculated as follows:

$$\varepsilon = \max_{i=1,2,\dots,n} l_i - \min_{i=1,2,\dots,n} l_i. \quad (6)$$

4. Term-weighting schemes and similarity measures

In this section, the different term-weighting schemes and similarity measures are described.

4.1. Term-weighting schemes

The related works from Section 2 considered three different term-weighting schemes: $tf - isf$, $rtf - sif$, and Okapi BM25.

Firstly, $tf - isf$ scheme is a combination of tf and isf (Salton & Buckley, 1988). On the one hand, tf_{ik} counts the number of times that the term t_k occurs in the sentence s_i . On the other hand, isf counts the number of sentences n_k of the document collection that contain the term t_k . The $tf - isf$ is calculated as follows:

$$w_{ik}^{tf-isf} = tf_{ik} \cdot \log(n/n_k), \quad (7)$$

where n is the number of sentences contained in the document collection.

Secondly, $rtf - sif$ scheme is presented. It is a modification of the previous scheme, based on the relative frequency of the term t_k in the document collection (Manning et al., 2008). Furthermore, the sif factor also includes a small modification, adding one more occurrence of the term. The $rtf - sif$ scheme is formulated as:

$$w_{ik}^{rtf-sif} = (tf_{ik}/maxFreq_i) \cdot \log(n/(1 + n_k)), \quad (8)$$

where $maxFreq_i$ indicates the number of times that the most frequent term occurs in the sentence s_i .

Finally, Okapi BM25 is another framework used to assign term weights according to their relevance (Robertson et al., 1995). In contrast to $tf - isf$ scheme, it is sensitive to the term frequency and the document length, so it normalizes the length of sentences. It is formulated as:

$$w_{ik}^{obm25} = \frac{tf_{ik}}{tf_{ik} + 0.5 + 1.5 \cdot l_i/l_{avg}} \cdot \log(n/n_k), \quad (9)$$

where l_i is the length of the sentence s_i and l_{avg} is the average length.

4.2. Similarity measures

A total of five similarity measures have been used in the scientific literature for multi-document text summarization and they have been presented in Section 2, i.e., cosine, Jaccard, overlap, RRN, and NGD.

In the first place, the cosine similarity, sim^{cos} , is the most used similarity measure in this context (Salton & Buckley, 1988). It measures the resemblance between two sentences s_i and s_j as follows:

$$sim^{cos}(s_i, s_j) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik}w_{jk}}{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik}^2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^m w_{jk}^2}}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (10)$$

where m is the number of different terms in the document collection.

In the second place, the Jaccard similarity, sim^{jac} , is another popular symmetric similarity measure in text mining (Alguliev et al., 2015), and it is calculated as follows:

$$sim^{jac}(s_i, s_j) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik}w_{jk}}{\sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik}^2 + \sum_{k=1}^m w_{jk}^2 - \sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik}w_{jk}}, \quad (11)$$

$$i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

In the third place, unlike the two previous measures, the overlap similarity, sim^{ove} , is asymmetric (Alguliev et al., 2015). An asymmetric similarity measure differs from a symmetric one in that the sentence ordering is relevant, i.e., $sim(s_i, s_j) \neq sim(s_j, s_i)$. The overlap similarity is formulated as follows:

$$sim^{ove}(s_i, s_j) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik}w_{jk}}{\sum_{k=1}^m w_{jk}^2}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (12)$$

In the fourth place, the RRN similarity, sim^{rrn} , is presented. It argues that, if there are many common terms between two sentences, then they are very similar (Alguliyev et al., 2015). It is defined as follows:

$$sim^{rrn}(s_i, s_j) = 1 - \frac{2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^m (w_{ik} - w_{ik}w_{jk}) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^m (w_{jk} - w_{ik}w_{jk})}{\sum_{k=1}^m w_{jk} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^m (w_{ik} - w_{ik}w_{jk}) + \sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^m (w_{jk} - w_{ik}w_{jk})}, \quad (13)$$

$$i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Finally, the NGD similarity measures the number of hits returned by the Google search engine for a given set of terms (Cilibrasi & Vitanyi, 2007).

The NGD applied to the text summarization problem as a similarity measure, sim^{ngd} , is presented in equations (14), (15), and (16):

$$sim^{ngd}(s_i, s_j) = \sum_{l=1}^m \left(\sum_{k=1}^m w_{ik} p_{kl} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^m w_{jk} p_{kl} \right), \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (14)$$

where p_{kl} is the similarity between the k -th term and the l -th term, which is calculated as follows:

$$p_{kl} = e^{-NGD_{kl}}, \quad (15)$$

where NGD_{kl} is the Normalized Google Distance between the k -th term and the l -th term, and it is calculated as follows:

$$NGD_{kl} = \frac{\max \{ \log(n_k), \log(n_l) \} - \log(n_{kl})}{\log(n) - \min \{ \log(n_k), \log(n_l) \}}, \quad (16)$$

where n_{kl} counts the number of sentences in the document collection which contain the k -th term and the l -th term.

5. Results

This section includes the datasets used for the experiments, the evaluation metrics, the experimental settings, and the results obtained.

5.1. Datasets

The multi-document summarization datasets provided by *Document Understanding Conferences* (DUC) have been used in this work. DUC is an open benchmark for generic automatic summarization evaluation from the *National Institute of Standards and Technology* (NIST). DUC2002 datasets have been considered (NIST, 2014), and several characteristics are presented in Table 2.

Description	Characteristics
Number of topics	10 (from d061j to d070f)
Number of documents in each topic	~ 8 (from 5 to 14)
Number of documents	77
Summary length constraint	200 words

Table 2: Some characteristics of the used topics from DUC2002 datasets.

Besides, the number of different terms and sentences for each used topic are shown in Table 3.

Topic	No. of terms	No. of sentences
d061j	693	184
d062j	630	118
d063j	846	249
d064j	924	183
d065j	1080	284
d066j	923	190
d067f	644	122
d068f	531	131
d069f	1306	327
d070f	620	148

Table 3: Number of different terms and sentences for each used topic from DUC2002 datasets.

5.2. Evaluation metrics

The *Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation* (ROUGE) metric has been used to evaluate all the experiments. This metric counts the number of overlapping units between a computer-generated summary and a human-generated summary (Lin, 2004). In addition, ROUGE is considered as the official evaluation metric by DUC for text summarization.

In this work, the four existing ROUGE scores have been used: ROUGE-N, ROUGE-L, ROUGE-W, and ROUGE-S. ROUGE-N is an N-gram recall between a candidate summary and a set of reference summaries. All ROUGE-N scores have been analyzed: ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-3, and ROUGE-4. Secondly, ROUGE-L computes the ratio between the length of the summaries' longest common subsequence and the length of the reference summary. Thirdly, ROUGE-W score, which is based on the weighted longest common subsequence, improves the basic longest common subsequence method by taking into account the consecutive matches' length found. ROUGE-S is a skip-bigram co-occurrence statistics which measures the overlap of skip-bigrams between a candidate summary and a set of reference summaries. Instead, ROUGE-SU (an extension of ROUGE-S) has been used, which is obtained by adding a unigram as counting unit. Finally, ROUGE-SU4, a skip-bigram with a maximum length of 4, has also been used.

Besides the average values, the Pearson’s coefficient of variation (CV) has been used to measure the relative dispersion of the ROUGE scores. It is expressed in percentage terms as follows:

$$CV = \frac{\sigma_{ROUGE}}{\overline{ROUGE}} \cdot 100, \quad (17)$$

being σ_{ROUGE} the standard deviation and \overline{ROUGE} the arithmetic mean of ROUGE values.

5.3. Experimental settings

The presented extractive multi-document text summarization problem was addressed by a Multi-Objective Artificial Bee Colony (MOABC) algorithm (Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2018), which has obtained, for this multi-objective problem, the best results found in the scientific literature. The following parameter setting for the algorithm provided excellent results: population size, $pop_{size} = 64$; mutation probability, $p_m = 0.1$; and number of cycles, $cycles_{max} = 1000$.

The hardware used for carrying out the experiments has been a compute node with 4 processors AMD Opteron Abu Dhabi 6376 2.3GHz, each one with 16 cores (a total of 64 cores), and 96GB RAM. As for the software, the approach has been implemented in C/C++ language, and Eclipse platform on Ubuntu 16.04 LTS has been used for the development. Specifically, the C/C++ compiler version has been GCC 5.3.0.

5.4. Experimental results

The experiments have been carried out for each combination of term-weighting scheme and similarity measure, i.e., the 15 possible combinations have been analyzed. Besides, for every experiment, a total of 20 repetitions have been performed. Tables 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, and 11 report the results for ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-3, ROUGE-4, ROUGE-L, ROUGE-W, ROUGE-SU, and ROUGE-SU4, respectively. The ROUGE score shown is the average result of the ten topics used.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.581	0.00%	0.570	0.00%	0.574	0.03%	0.577	0.42%	0.566	0.65%	0.574	0.22%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.570	0.00%	0.563	0.00%	0.564	0.00%	0.568	0.61%	0.578	0.18%	0.569	0.16%
w^{obm25}	0.566	0.53%	0.572	0.00%	0.565	0.59%	0.567	0.47%	0.557	1.03%	0.565	0.52%
Average	0.572	0.18%	0.569	0.00%	0.568	0.21%	0.571	0.50%	0.567	0.62%		

Table 4: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-1 score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.336	0.00%	0.331	0.00%	0.331	0.00%	0.320	0.90%	0.305	1.22%	0.325	0.42%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.299	0.00%	0.284	0.00%	0.292	0.00%	0.303	1.33%	0.289	0.27%	0.294	0.32%
w^{obm25}	0.306	1.36%	0.316	0.00%	0.307	1.00%	0.314	0.91%	0.293	3.65%	0.307	1.38%
Average	0.314	0.45%	0.311	0.00%	0.310	0.33%	0.313	1.05%	0.296	1.71%		

Table 5: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-2 score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.281	0.00%	0.270	0.00%	0.275	0.00%	0.263	0.79%	0.248	1.13%	0.267	0.38%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.235	0.00%	0.223	0.00%	0.236	0.00%	0.245	1.79%	0.232	0.12%	0.234	0.38%
w^{obm25}	0.246	1.81%	0.261	0.00%	0.250	0.77%	0.259	1.01%	0.236	4.30%	0.250	1.58%
Average	0.254	0.60%	0.251	0.00%	0.254	0.26%	0.256	1.19%	0.239	1.85%		

Table 6: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-3 score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.261	0.00%	0.252	0.00%	0.257	0.00%	0.243	0.81%	0.231	1.12%	0.249	0.39%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.217	0.00%	0.204	0.00%	0.219	0.00%	0.227	1.83%	0.214	0.08%	0.216	0.38%
w^{obm25}	0.228	1.62%	0.242	0.00%	0.230	0.51%	0.240	1.01%	0.220	4.42%	0.232	1.51%
Average	0.235	0.54%	0.233	0.00%	0.235	0.17%	0.237	1.21%	0.222	1.87%		

Table 7: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-4 score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.551	0.00%	0.552	0.00%	0.554	0.02%	0.554	0.44%	0.538	0.66%	0.550	0.22%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.547	0.00%	0.535	0.00%	0.534	0.00%	0.545	0.60%	0.544	0.17%	0.541	0.15%
w^{obm25}	0.538	0.46%	0.544	0.00%	0.540	0.54%	0.542	0.47%	0.532	1.23%	0.539	0.54%
Average	0.546	0.15%	0.544	0.00%	0.542	0.19%	0.547	0.50%	0.538	0.69%		

Table 8: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-L score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.183	0.00%	0.177	0.00%	0.176	0.00%	0.178	0.59%	0.172	0.78%	0.177	0.27%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.173	0.00%	0.170	0.03%	0.168	0.00%	0.171	0.90%	0.175	0.46%	0.172	0.28%
w^{obm25}	0.168	0.79%	0.178	0.00%	0.169	0.43%	0.170	0.52%	0.167	1.31%	0.171	0.61%
Average	0.175	0.26%	0.175	0.01%	0.171	0.14%	0.173	0.67%	0.172	0.85%		

Table 9: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-W score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.316	0.00%	0.308	0.00%	0.311	0.00%	0.306	0.62%	0.283	1.28%	0.305	0.38%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.291	0.00%	0.282	0.02%	0.282	0.05%	0.290	0.77%	0.307	0.27%	0.290	0.22%
w^{obm25}	0.295	0.83%	0.303	0.00%	0.293	1.56%	0.301	0.75%	0.291	2.19%	0.297	1.06%
Average	0.301	0.28%	0.298	0.01%	0.295	0.54%	0.299	0.71%	0.293	1.25%		

Table 10: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-SU score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

Combination	sim^{cos}		sim^{jac}		sim^{ove}		sim^{rrn}		sim^{ngd}		Average	
	Avg.	CV	Avg.	CV								
w^{tf-isf}	0.319	0.00%	0.311	0.00%	0.314	0.00%	0.308	2.62%	0.285	1.27%	0.307	0.38%
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.293	0.00%	0.285	0.02%	0.285	0.05%	0.293	0.77%	0.309	0.26%	0.293	0.22%
w^{obm25}	0.298	0.82%	0.305	0.00%	0.296	1.54%	0.303	0.75%	0.294	2.16%	0.299	1.06%
Average	0.303	0.27%	0.300	0.01%	0.298	0.53%	0.301	0.71%	0.296	1.23%		

Table 11: Average (Avg.) and CV for ROUGE-SU4 score of the ten topics used. The combinations with the best value and the best average value appear in grey background.

From the results reported in Tables 4 to 11, the following points can be concluded. In the first place, the results regarding the term-weighting schemes are analyzed. In this case, the $tf - isf$ scheme achieves the best

average values in the eight ROUGE scores, so it is the best term-weighting scheme. The Okapi BM25 scheme, w^{obm25} , has achieved the second best average value, obtaining the second best values in five out of eight ROUGE scores: ROUGE-2, ROUGE-3, ROUGE-4, ROUGE-SU, and ROUGE-SU4. Lastly, the $rtf - sisf$ scheme has obtained the second best values for ROUGE-1, ROUGE-L, and ROUGE-W, being the third term-weighting scheme in average terms. In addition, the combination that obtains the best result always has the $tf - isf$ scheme as term-weighting scheme. With the purpose of showing the improvement of the $tf - isf$ scheme over the other two schemes, Table 12 is presented. It shows the percentage improvement of the $tf - isf$ scheme over the average of the other two term-weighting schemes for each ROUGE score.

Term-weighting scheme	ROUGE-1	ROUGE-2	ROUGE-3	ROUGE-4	ROUGE-L	ROUGE-W	ROUGE-SU	ROUGE-SU4
w^{tf-isf}	0.574	0.325	0.267	0.249	0.550	0.177	0.305	0.307
$w^{rtf-sisf}$	0.569	0.294	0.234	0.216	0.541	0.172	0.290	0.293
w^{obm25}	0.565	0.307	0.250	0.232	0.539	0.171	0.297	0.299
Average improvement of w^{tf-isf}	1.24%	8.20%	10.45%	11.30%	1.85%	3.21%	3.93%	3.73%

Table 12: Percentage improvement of the $tf - isf$ scheme over the average of the other term-weighting schemes for each ROUGE score.

Table 12 reports that the $tf - isf$ scheme achieves percentage improvements in all ROUGE scores in average terms. Moreover, these improvements are greater than 1% in all of them. Specifically, the percentage improvement ranges between 1.24% and 11.30% (an average improvement of 5.49%). The largest differences occur in ROUGE-2, ROUGE-3, and ROUGE-4, where the percentage improvement is around 10%. As it can be seen in equations (7), (8), and (9), despite the fact that the mathematical formulation complexity is similar among the different term-weighting schemes, the $tf - isf$ scheme provides significant result improvements compared to the $rtf - sisf$ and Okapi BM25 schemes. Furthermore, Figure 1 shows, graphically, these percentage improvements of the $tf - isf$ scheme.

Figure 1: Percentage improvement of the $tf - isf$ scheme over the average of the other term-weighting schemes for each ROUGE score.

In the second place, regarding the similarity measures, the cosine similarity obtains the best averages in most of ROUGE scores (5 out of 8): ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-W, ROUGE-SU, and ROUGE-SU4. In addition, it obtains the second best average values in the rest of ROUGE scores. The RRN similarity achieves the best average values in ROUGE-3, ROUGE-4, and ROUGE-L, and it obtains the second best average values in the ones in which the cosine similarity achieves the best results (ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-W, ROUGE-SU, and ROUGE-SU4). The Jaccard similarity has also achieved the same average value as the cosine similarity for ROUGE-W score, obtaining the third best average values in five out of eight ROUGE scores: ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-L, ROUGE-SU, and ROUGE-SU4. In the rest of ROUGE scores, on the one hand, both the cosine similarity and the overlap similarity have obtained the second best average values for ROUGE-3 and ROUGE-4 scores. On the other hand, the RRN similarity has obtained the third best average value for ROUGE-W score. From this analysis it can be concluded that the best similarity measure is the cosine similarity, while the second one is the RRN similarity. The Jaccard similarity, the overlap similarity, and the NGD similarity are the third, fourth, and fifth similarities, respectively. The two first similarity measures have always obtained the best results in combination with the $tf - isf$ scheme

(see Tables 4 to 11). Similarly to the $tf - isf$ scheme improvement analysis, Table 13 shows the percentage improvement of the cosine similarity over the average of the other four similarity measures for each ROUGE score.

Similarity measure	ROUGE-1	ROUGE-2	ROUGE-3	ROUGE-4	ROUGE-L	ROUGE-W	ROUGE-SU	ROUGE-SU4
sim^{cos}	0.572	0.314	0.254	0.235	0.546	0.175	0.301	0.303
sim^{jac}	0.569	0.311	0.251	0.233	0.544	0.175	0.298	0.300
sim^{ove}	0.568	0.310	0.254	0.235	0.542	0.171	0.295	0.298
sim^{rrn}	0.571	0.313	0.256	0.237	0.547	0.173	0.299	0.301
sim^{ngd}	0.567	0.296	0.239	0.222	0.538	0.172	0.293	0.296
Average improvement of sim^{cos}	0.57%	2.16%	1.67%	1.47%	0.60%	1.31%	1.61%	1.43%

Table 13: Percentage improvement of the cosine similarity over the average of the other similarity measures for each ROUGE score.

Table 13 reports that the cosine similarity obtains percentage improvements in all ROUGE scores in average terms. Specifically, it achieves improvements greater than 1% in 6 out of 8 ROUGE scores, and the percentage improvement ranges between 0.57% and 2.16% (an average improvement of 1.35%). In this case, the largest differences take place in ROUGE-2, ROUGE-3, and ROUGE-SU, where the percentage improvement is over 1.5%. In addition, equations (10), (11), (12), (13), and (14) show that there are some differences among the mathematical formulation complexities of the different similarity measures. Particularly, the complexity of the cosine similarity is similar to the complexity of the Jaccard similarity, and the cosine similarity achieves better results. Regarding the complexity of the overlap similarity, it is less than the complexity of the cosine similarity, but its results are worse. Finally, the complexities of the RRN and NGD similarities are greater than the complexity of the cosine similarity, also providing worse results. Figure 2 shows, graphically, the percentage improvements of the cosine similarity.

Figure 2: Percentage improvement of the cosine similarity over the average of the other similarity measures for each ROUGE score.

As conclusion, the results from Tables 12 and 13 report that the best term-weighting scheme is the $tf - isf$ scheme (w^{tf-isf}), just like the best similarity measure is the cosine similarity (sim^{cos}). Furthermore, from Tables 4 to 11 it can be noted that the combination formed by them, (w^{tf-isf} , sim^{cos}), obtains the best results in 7 out of 8 ROUGE scores (with the exception of ROUGE-L score, where the combinations (w^{tf-isf} , sim^{ove}) and (w^{tf-isf} , sim^{rrn}) obtain the best result). Therefore, the best combination of term-weighting scheme and similarity measure is the one formed by the $tf - isf$ scheme and the cosine similarity, (w^{tf-isf} , sim^{cos}).

Finally, the execution times of all the term-weighting schemes and all the similarity measures are presented. The aim is to compare the computational costs. First, the average execution times obtained for each term-weighting scheme and for each used topic are shown in Table 14.

Topic	Term-weighting scheme		
	w^{tf-isf}	$w^{rtf-sisf}$	w^{obm25}
d061j	83.740	83.286	86.901
d062j	31.169	31.576	33.944
d063j	168.376	173.774	177.543
d064j	113.639	111.490	115.710
d065j	268.905	269.157	285.730
d066j	111.857	111.826	117.052
d067f	35.791	36.831	38.733
d068f	30.551	30.760	33.555
d069f	536.101	536.631	551.262
d070f	48.188	49.124	50.658
Average	142.832	143.446	149.109

Table 14: Execution times (in seconds) for each used topic for the three term-weighting schemes and average execution times.

The average execution times presented in Table 14 show that the $tf - isf$ scheme is the fastest one. The $rtf - sisf$ scheme is the second fastest, and the Okapi BM25 scheme is the slowest. Hence, the $tf - isf$ scheme not only provides the best average ROUGE results, but is also the fastest term-weighting scheme.

In the second place, Table 15 shows the average execution times obtained for each similarity measure and with each used topic.

Topic	Similarity measure				
	sim^{cos}	sim^{jac}	sim^{ove}	sim^{rrn}	sim^{ngd}
d061j	1.415	1.455	1.034	1.961	455.330
d062j	0.525	0.554	0.384	0.766	153.591
d063j	3.223	3.590	2.356	4.426	1997.963
d064j	1.857	1.899	1.469	2.751	808.595
d065j	5.366	5.288	4.374	7.330	2596.483
d066j	2.040	2.056	1.472	2.781	878.341
d067f	0.567	0.593	0.422	0.795	170.301
d068f	0.552	0.561	0.441	0.744	132.438
d069f	9.856	8.786	6.131	12.149	5019.480
d070f	0.823	0.836	0.602	1.132	233.664
Average	2.622	2.562	1.869	3.484	1244.619

Table 15: Execution times (in seconds) for each used topic for the five similarity measures and average execution times.

Table 15 reports the existence of two groups of similarity measures according to their average execution times. On the one hand, the group with the first four similarity measures obtains average execution times between one and three seconds: the overlap similarity, sim^{ove} , the Jaccard similarity, sim^{jac} , the cosine similarity, sim^{cos} , and the RRN similarity, sim^{rrn} . On the other hand, the NGD similarity obtains a very high execution time with respect to the previous ones. Furthermore, the cosine similarity, in addition to obtain the best average ROUGE results, is one of the fastest similarity measures.

The final conclusions can be summarized in the following points. First, the $tf - isf$ scheme is the best term-weighting scheme because it achieves the best average values in all the ROUGE scores, being also the fastest term-weighting scheme. Second, the cosine similarity is the best similarity measure, achieving the best average values in five out of eight ROUGE scores, and it is one of the fastest similarity measures. And finally, the combination formed by them, (w^{tf-isf}, sim^{cos}) , achieves the best average values in seven out of eight ROUGE scores.

6. Conclusions and future research

Automatic summarization of multiple digital documents is increasingly necessary. In fact, extractive multi-document text summarization is a matter of great interest in recent years. Its formulation can be defined in multiple ways, since there is a wide variety of term-weighting schemes and similarity measures in the scientific literature. Nevertheless, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no studies that have analyzed and compared the differences among these schemes and measures. For this reason, in this paper, a comparative study of the different term-weighting schemes and similarity measures has been carried out in order to analyze their impact on the extractive multi-document text summarization problem, from both points of view: summary quality and computational cost. The term-weighting schemes studied have been: term-frequency inverse-sentence-frequency scheme ($tf - isf$), relative-term-frequency smooth-inverse-sentence-frequency scheme ($rtf - sif$), and Okapi BM25 scheme. On the other side, the similarity measures analyzed have been the following ones: cosine, Jaccard, overlap, RRN, and NGD.

All the possible combinations of term-weighting schemes and similarity measures have been experimented, analyzed, and compared, that is, a total of 15 different combinations. As evaluation metrics, 8 different ROUGE scores (the standard in the field) and the execution time have been used, generating an exhaustive comparative study. This study clearly presents the relative quality and computational cost among the different combinations of term-weighting schemes and similarity measures. As best alternatives, the results obtained show that the $tf - isf$ scheme has achieved the best average results in all ROUGE scores, and the cosine similarity has obtained the best average results in 62.5% of ROUGE scores. Furthermore, the combination formed by the $tf - isf$ scheme and the cosine similarity, (w^{tf-isf}, sim^{cos}), has achieved the best average results in 87.5% of ROUGE scores. Regarding the execution time, the $tf - isf$ scheme is the fastest term-weighting scheme, and the cosine similarity is one of the fastest similarity measures. Therefore, it can be concluded that this combination (w^{tf-isf}, sim^{cos}) obtains very good results from both points of view: summary quality and computational cost.

A future research is the development of an automatic summarization tool in NeuroK software¹. NeuroK is an e-learning platform based on neurodi-

¹<https://neurok.es/en/>

dactics and social network principles (Calle-Alonso et al., 2017). The goal is to generate a summary from the text that the students write in the learning units or in the learning activities of a specific course. In this way, teachers will be able to carry out an easier follow-up of the student's learning process. Additionally, the tool could provide an automatic grade of the student's summary by comparing it with a summary proposed by the teacher.

Another future research line is the use of word embeddings techniques as similarity measures. In this way, the inclusion of linguistic and semantic information obtained from an input text corpus as, for example, the *word2vec* model (Mikolov et al., 2013) could provide interesting results.

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